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Research Article

**STETHOSCOPE AS AN INFECTION SOURCE: OCCURRENCE
OF BACTERIAL COLONIZATION ON THE STETHOSCOPE**¹Dr Qammar Sultan, ²Muhammad Farjad Yousof, ³Kamran Ali¹MO, RHC Hajipur Distt Rajan Pur²Medical Officer at DHQ Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan³Medical Officer at THQ Kot Chutta**Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Objectives: The aim of this research work was to find out the occurrence of bacterial colonization on the stethoscope in different departments of the hospital and know about the impact of the education of the staff to decrease that infectivity.

Methodology: The swabs of the bacteriological culture gathered from the doctors, students of medical field, trainees & nurses working in various departments. A movement was initiated and all the staff was advised to clean their stethoscopes consistently with the wipes of alcohol after use every time. After one-week period, the swabs of the bacteriological culture were performed again and testing of antibiotic sensitivity performed. The habit of the staff of clean-up the stethoscopes was put into comparison pre and post of the clean movement.

Results: The swabbing of 92 stethoscopes was carried out; forty-seven in the 1st week and forty-five in the 2nd week. In the 1st week, forty-four stethoscopes found positive for SA (staphylococcus aureus). In the 2nd week, thirty-eight stethoscopes + cultures, staphylococcus epidermidis was growing on all of them. No culture was + for MRSA (methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus) in any week. This amount of units of colony forming decreased from median of twenty in 1st week to median of eight in the 2nd week. The awareness to the staff led to high rate of cleaning of stethoscopes.

Conclusion: Pathogens are available on the stethoscopes but the education of staff and alterations in the habits of stethoscope cleaning decrease the danger initiated by this important medical instrument.

Key Words: Stethoscope, aureus, danger, methods, pathogens, hospital, nurse.

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INTRODUCTION:

NI (Nosocomial infections) is very frequent cause of the morbidity & mortality in the patients who are hospitalized. About five to ten percent patients may get the infections from the hospital [1]. With high morbidity & mortality, these findings are the extra economic burden on the overall system of healthcare [1, 2]. Stethoscopes are one of the main causes of these infections [1, 2]. Staphylococcus epidermidis is very frequent bacteria separated from the parts of stethoscopes [3]. Madar concluded species of Staphylococcus in eighty-five percent of samples of stethoscopes. Marinella sampled forty stethoscopes & displayed Staphylococcus aureus colorizations on all the collected samples. The development of other microbes is a controversial issue as growth of E.Coli [1, 4].

In the year of 1860, Ignaz Semmelweis concluded that the hygiene of hand considerably decreased mortality [5]. The germ theory of Louis Pasteur confirmed his findings. Currently, the spread of these infections has association with the other sources as electronic thermometers, cuffs of blood pressure, gloves, computer terminals [6] and Doppler probes [1]. The professionals of the healthcare departments are frequently using the stethoscopes which are not cleaned on regular basis [3, 7]. various substances are in use to diminish the germs from the surfaces of the stethoscopes [1, 2, 4]. Isopropylene alcohol has a better impact on the decrease of the bacteria [8]. But the role of this medical instrument in the spreading of these infections including respiratory virus has not been confirmed yet [2]. No research work in this topic has yet claimed the separation of the Clostridium difficile from this medical instrument [8]. The objective of this research work was to find out the occurrence of the colonization of germs on stethoscopes & evaluate the effectiveness of the regular agents of cleaning and the role of the professionals in the healthcare department in the decrease of the occurrence of this colonization.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work was an audit. About 92 stethoscopes utilized by doctors, students of medical field, trainees, nurses & physiotherapists were the samples. The collection of the cultures carried out from the direct impression on stethoscopes diaphragm onto agar plates of blood. ABAP (Anaerobic blood agar plates) were carried to the laboratory & incubation of the samples carried out at thirty-seven centigrade for forty-eight hours. Identification of the microbes cultured on the plates carried out and their measurement carried out with the help of CFU (colony forming units). Antibiotic sensitivity conducted on some selected samples. Stethoscopes diaphragms were cultured two times in a period of fourteen days (forty-seven in the 1st week & forty-seven in the 2nd week). Every participant filled a questionnaire about the stethoscopes cleaning and cleaning agent which was being used by them. Random technique used for their selection in 1st week and asked to use alcohol wipes to clean their stethoscopes after every use. Swabbing of these stethoscopes after one week and same questionnaire was filled to know about the routine of cleaning of stethoscope & impact on the education of the staff. P value of <0.05 was the significant.

RESULTS:

Forty-seven stethoscopes sampled in the 1st week & forty-five in the 2nd week. Among the participants, there were four consultants, forty trainees, one medical students, forty-seven nurses & physiotherapists. The collection of the samples carried out from different departments, thirty-three from surgical, thirty-four from medical, seven from pediatrics, twelve from anesthetic & seven from gynecology. In the 1st week, positive culture was available on forty-six out of forty-seven stethoscopes. The microbes separated from the instrument were Staphylococcus aureus (forty-four) & staphylococcus epidermidis (two). In the 2nd week, thirty-eight out of forty-five were found with the positive culture. The separated microbes were S epidermidis in all the + cultures and none of the instrument found with + for Staphylococcus aureus as described in Table-1.

Table-I: Type of the organisms isolated before and after the campaign

Organism	Staphylococcus epidermidis	Staphylococcus aureus	No Growth
1st Week	2.00	44.00	1.00
2nd Week	38.00	0.00	7.00

The load of bacteria as calculated by the CFU has decreased after the education of the staff in the 2nd week. A CFU median of twenty were separated from in the 1st week, whereas, a CFU median of eight isolated in the 2nd week from the stethoscopes which were cultured. The habit of stethoscope cleaning was change in the 2nd week as displayed in the questionnaire. In the 2nd week, the participants who were regularly cleaning their stethoscopes increased from twelve out of forty-seven to twenty-five out of forty-five participants as mentioned in Table-2.

Table-II: Frequency of cleaning before and after staff education

	Frequently (after every patient, daily)	Less frequently (weekly, monthly)
1st Week	12.00	35.00
2nd Week	25.00	20.00

DISCUSSION:

Nosocomial infections are very common in recent times and their administration is very difficult and not cheap. Up to ten percent patients get an infection at the time of their stay in the hospital. This reason creates an important monetary load on expensive system of healthcare. Stethoscopes can be recognized as the source of nosocomial infections and have a bacteria potential vector. The education of the

occupational staff in the healthcare department regarding this matter is very important. The findings of this research work show that up to ninety-four percent stethoscopes have the bacteria of infection on their diaphragm as *Staphylococcus aureus*. This percentage is very high. The education of the staff and alterations in the habits of cleaning has the ability to reduce the amount of the contamination & can decrease the danger of nosocomial infections.

There were some limitations of this research work. The amount of the cultured stethoscopes was not much enough to make generalizations. We did not gather information about episodes of nosocomial infections that happened during the 2 stages of this research work to permit association & to display the real impacts on the patients. Though, even their collection carried out it was not possible to display important disparities because of low occurrence of nosocomial infections in our medical institute. MRSA (Methicillin resistant S-aureus), Clostridium difficile & other dangerous organisms' isolation carried out in the start from stethoscopes & from other instrument of the hospital [1, 4, 6]. Though, in this research work, we failed to separate those pathogens though e was directly targeting these bacteria.

This is the outcome of the hard methods in place which contains energetic screening of patients & carrier's isolation or simply because of short size of samples. These pathogens created a danger for the patients and stethoscopes can be a reservoir for all of the pathogens. The professionals of the healthcare department play an important role in the prevention of nosocomial infections. In this research work, education of the staff caused the more regular stethoscope cleaning as displayed by the questionnaires completed in 2 stages of the research work. In the 2nd week, both amount of CFUs & amount of the + cultures were considerably less. There were no ideal rules in our medical institute about the cleaning of the stethoscope at the time of this research work. We can reduce the contamination due to these pathogens with the existence and application of such policy.

CONCLUSIONS:

The conclusions of this research work proved that stethoscopes carry the important microbes of the infections. Doctors, nurses & all the professionals of the healthcare department required to be more active with their role in the transmissions of diseases because of their instruments.

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